

1 **Eco-friendly composite materials of polybutylene succinate with clay minerals,**
2 **lignin and canabrava fiber**

3 Lucas Nao Horiuchi^a, Raquel de Melo Barbosa^{b*}, Joyce Batista Azevedo^c, Fátima
4 Garcia Villen^d, César Viseras^{d,e}, Rosana Lopes Lima Fialho^{a*}

5 ^a Postgraduate Program in Industrial Engineering – PEI, Federal University of Bahia,
6 Salvador 40.210-630, Bahia, Brazil; lucas.horiuchi@ufba.br, rosanafialho@ufba.br

7 ^b Department of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Technology, School of Pharmacy, C/
8 Professor García González, 2. 41012, Seville, Spain; rdemelo@us.es

9 ^c Institute of Science, Technology and Innovation, Federal University of Bahia, Salvador
10 42809-000, Bahia, Brazil; joyce.azevedo@ufba.br

11 ^dDepartment of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Technology, School of Pharmacy, Campus
12 of Cartuja s/n, University of Granada, 18071 Granada, Spain; fgarvillen@ugr.es

13 ^eAndalusian Institute of Earth Sciences, CSIC-University of Granada, Av. de Las
14 Palmeras, Armilla, 18100 Granada, Spain; cviseras@ugr.es

15 * **Correspondence:** rdemelo@us.es and rosanafialho@ufba.br

16 **Abstract:** The widespread use of plastics in seedling production, due to their convenience
17 and cost-effectiveness, poses significant environmental challenges, including pollution
18 and high resource consumption. To address these issues, a sustainable hybrid bio-
19 composite was developed using bio-polybutylene succinate (PBS) combined with
20 canabrava fibers (Cana) (up to 30 wt.%), lignin (Lig), montmorillonite (MMT), and
21 sepiolite (SEP). This bio-composite, featuring a negative carbon footprint and fully
22 biodegradable components, offers a promising alternative to polypropylene packaging in
23 seedling production, enhancing environmental sustainability and promoting the
24 valorization of waste materials like Cana and Lig. The bio-composites were synthesized
25 via melt blending in an extruder, and their mechanical, thermal, and morphological

26 properties were evaluated. The melt flow rate could be effectively managed by adjusting
27 the combination of Cana, Lig, and clays, achieving values comparable to polypropylene
28 (EP440L). Notable enhancements in mechanical properties were observed relative to neat
29 PBS, with increases in Young's modulus (up to 353%), yield stress (up to 198%), flexural
30 modulus (up to 390%), and flexural strength (up to 160%). These improvements are
31 mainly attributed to the high Cana fiber content and the hybrid effects of clays,
32 particularly SEP. However, reductions in impact resistance and elongation were noted
33 compared to neat PBS and EP440L, likely due to limited fiber-polymer interactions and
34 increased compactness as observed in SEM analysis. FT-IR analysis indicated strong
35 interactions between clays and PBS, evidenced by a shoulder at 1602-1608 cm^{-1} . XRD
36 analysis suggested the exfoliation of MMT, as indicated by the absence of the (001) plane
37 reflection, although the high content of Cana may have mitigated some mechanical
38 benefits. DSC analysis revealed increased crystallinity with the incorporation of Cana,
39 Lig, and clays, likely driven by nucleation effects. The presence of SEP was associated
40 with a secondary melting peak, indicating effective dispersion and interfacial crystal
41 formation. Enhanced thermal stability was demonstrated by a higher temperature at 90%
42 mass loss compared to neat PBS. These findings suggest the bio-composite is a
43 sustainable alternative for reducing plastic waste in seedling production.

44 **Keywords:** PBS, canabrava; lignin, montmorillonite; sepiolite; bio-composites.

45

46 **1. Introduction**

47 Polybutylene Succinate (PBS) is acknowledged as a biodegradable and sustainable
48 polymer, primarily due to its capability to be produced from renewable sources. This
49 feature distinguishes it as a viable alternative to petroleum-derived polymers, as
50 evidenced by some authors (Bozell and Petersen, 2010; Kuenz et al., 2020; Barletta et al.,

51 2022). As an aliphatic polyester, PBS is synthesized through the polycondensation of
52 succinic acid with 1,4-butanediol using ring-opening polymerization or enzymatic
53 polymerization methods. This process endows PBS with properties comparable to those
54 of low-density polyethylene and polypropylene, such as a melting temperature of 110°C
55 and a glass transition temperature of -36°C (Li et al., 2017), coupled with the significant
56 advantage of biodegradability (Sisti et al., 2016).

57 Overall, the versatility of PBS arises from its biodegradability, compatibility with other
58 polymers and the possibility of using renewable sources for its production (obtention of
59 PBS monomers). Regardless of whether they originate from bio-renewable or fossil
60 sources, these monomers confer desirable mechanical properties to PBS while
61 maintaining compatibility with conventional processing techniques such as extrusion and
62 injection. The development of compostable plastics, exemplified by PBS, which degrade
63 into natural components like water, carbon dioxide, and biomass, has propelled the use
64 of this material in a variety of fields, from biological packaging to the textile sector (PTT
65 MCC Biochem, 2023). However, it still shows some limitations such as low mechanical
66 strength and modulus (stiffness) (Someya et al., 2003), unsatisfactory gas barrier
67 properties, slow crystallization rate, high flammability, and high costs that limit its
68 application in other areas (Zhang et al., 2019).

69 To overcome these challenges, various strategies have been explored, including
70 copolymerization techniques, polymer blends, and the incorporation of different types of
71 reinforcements, as natural fiber in natural state or modified as cellulose nano fibril (CNF)
72 or cellulose nanocrystal (CNC) or micro fibrillated cellulose (MFC) (Joy et al., 2017). In
73 this regard, it is of utmost importance to appropriately select the reinforcing ingredients
74 to maintain PBS environmental friendliness. To do so, nanofillers (Joy et al., 2017) and
75 natural fibers (Mochane et al., 2021) such as sisal, cotton, sugarcane bagasse, and

76 bamboo, among others, have been successfully employed (Aaliya et al., 2021; Mochane
77 et al., 2021). In particular, canabrava (Cana) (*Gynerium sagittatum*) stands out as a natural
78 fiber with promising potential for sustainable PBS composite production. Primarily
79 derived as waste from basketry and handicrafts made by local communities in Brazil,
80 Cana exemplifies the concept of complete resource utilization. Its versatility extends to
81 fodder and cellulose production, making it a standout model of sustainability (Coradin et
82 al., 2011).

83 However, the addition of natural fibers usually increases the melt viscosity of the
84 polymer, which can compromise injection molding capability. The introduction of Lig,
85 isolated from the cellulose matrix complex, as a lubricant during melt processing, has
86 emerged as an innovative solution to this challenge, increasing the melt flow rate and,
87 consequently, facilitating injection processing. Moreover, the integration of Lig into
88 polymer composites not only improves thermal stability but also enhances their
89 antioxidant and antibacterial properties, in addition to reinforcing mechanical integrity.
90 This incorporation marks a significant advancement in the pursuit of environmental
91 sustainability of composites (Shah et al., 2023).

92 Further PBS improvements can be achieved by other additives such as natural inorganic
93 ingredients. The incorporation of clay minerals such as sepiolite (SEP) and
94 montmorillonite (MMT), emerges as an innovative and effective approach in material
95 engineering, particularly in enhancing polymeric composites like PBS. SEP,
96 characterized by its unique fibrous structure with internal mesoporous channels, exhibits
97 significant microporosity and an extensive specific surface area. This peculiar
98 morphology not only facilitates the interaction with the polymer and fibers but also
99 contributes to an increase in mechanical strength and composite density (leading to higher

100 viscosities and viscoelastic properties), in addition to acting as a flame retardant (Chikh
101 et al., 2016; Huo et al., 2017; García-Quiles et al., 2019).

102 MMT, stands out for its unique properties of cation exchange capacity, adsorption, and
103 swelling. This clay mineral, known for intercalating water molecules and metallic cations
104 between its layers, has also the ability to “intercalate” polymer fibers between its layers
105 (under the appropriate conditions), thus tuning the polymer properties and, ultimately,
106 leading to exfoliation, which increases the specific surface area and exposes active sites
107 for chemical reactions and physical interactions with polymeric matrices. The presence
108 of cations such as iron, vanadium, and lanthanides, which can be released or exchanged,
109 enriches the catalytic, mechanical, and barrier properties of composites. These
110 characteristics not only facilitate the integration and dispersion of the mineral into
111 composites but also enhance stiffness, thermal stability, conductivity, and gas barrier
112 properties, making MMT an indispensable additive for the development of advanced and
113 efficient composite materials, as evidenced by previous research (Zhong et al., 2016;
114 García-Quiles et al., 2019).

115 The strategic addition of clay minerals, such as SEP and MMT, to PBS composites marks
116 notable progress in the manufacture of advanced and sustainable materials. This
117 combination enriches PBS, concurrently improving its mechanical, thermal, flame
118 resistance, and barrier properties, thereby overcoming previous challenges related to
119 stiffness, permeability, and thermal stability. This advancement could potentially expand
120 the applications of PBS in other demanding sectors, emphasizing innovation and
121 sustainability in the creation of new materials. Studies such as those (Zhong et al., 2016;
122 García-Quiles et al., 2019; Rashid et al., 2021) demonstrate this efficacy, highlighting the
123 significant potential for the engineering of more efficient and environmentally
124 responsible materials.

125 Traditionally, packaging materials used for agricultural purposes are manufactured in
126 anti-UV photostabilized polypropylene, often incorporating ethylene-propylene
127 terpolymer (EPDM) (IBF, 2023). These non-biodegradable polymers, typically used only
128 once due to cost and logistical challenges, contribute significantly to environmental
129 pollution. This highlights the urgent need for more sustainable alternatives to reduce the
130 environmental impact. Thus, the aim of this study is to develop a biodegradable composite
131 material with a significant content of Cana natural fiber, aiming at cost reduction
132 compared to pure PBS. This material will be used in the manufacture of PBS tubes and
133 trays designed for agricultural planting (this study does not intend to work with
134 nanocellulose at this time). To do so, PBS properties and performance will be tuned by
135 natural additives such as Cana, Lig, SEP and MMT. The resultant bio-composite
136 alternatives aim to offer an environmentally friendly solution to the current use of non-
137 biodegradable plastic bags and tubes in seedling agriculture. Tubes have technical
138 advantages over bags due to their innovative design that incorporates grooves to
139 effectively guide the growth of plant roots and thus prevent destabilization during
140 transplantation.

141 **2. Experimental**

142 *2.1. Materials*

143 The bio-PBS was provided by PTT-MCC Biochem, with melt flow rate (MFR) value of
144 22 g/10min (190°C, 2.16 kg), melting temperature of 115°C, glass transition temperature
145 of -36°C, and density of 1.26 g/cm³. Lig (kraft) was kindly gifted by a brazilian cellulose
146 company. The Cana fiber was obtained as a residue from handcraft production by a local
147 community in Salvador, Bahia, Brazil (Ilha de Maré). This residue was in the form of
148 long strips of 1 to 2 m in length, and was crushed using a TRE40MA crusher (Tramontina
149 S.A., Carlos Barbosa, Brazil) in order to reduce the size to a few centimeters. And then it

150 was blended in a LQL8BIVMF60N5 blender (BIMG Ltda, Brusque, Brazil), and sieved
151 to obtain fibers with a mean length of 3.18 ± 1.90 mm and a width of 0.45 ± 0.23 mm,
152 calculated using optical microscope and the software ImageJ, analyzing more than one
153 thousand fibers, and the image of Cana fiber by optical microscopy is available in the
154 Supplementary Material (SM1), which can be accessed online. The MMT K10 (Sigma-
155 Aldrich Co., St Louis, USA) with a surface area of 220 to 270 m²/g and SEP type PS9
156 (Pangel S9, Tolsa S.A., Madrid, Spain) of high purity, specific surface area (BET, N₂) of
157 344 m²/g and total pore volume of 0.4476 cm³. Both clays were used with no
158 modification.

159 The results of PBS composites analysis were compared to Braskem's EP440L
160 polypropylene resin, which is a heterophasic copolymer of medium fluidity and indicated
161 for the injection molding process, for the manufacture of tubes for agriculture. According
162 to the manufacturer, the EP440L has a flow rate of 6.0 g/10min (at 230°C / 2.16 kg),
163 flexural modulus of 1050 MPa, flow resistance of 24 MPa, flow elongation of 6%,
164 Rockwell hardness 60 (R scale), Izod impact resistance at 23°C without rupture (at -20°C
165 of 75 J/m), thermal deflection temperature of 85°C (at 0.455 MPa) (Braskem S.A., 2018).

166

167 *2.2. Preparation of hybrid bio-composites*

168 All materials were dried in an oven to extract moisture and prevent PBS hydro-
169 degradation (Abderrahim et al., 2015; Muthuraj et al., 2015) that is potentiated by water
170 and high temperature during extrusion processing. The optimum drying conditions were
171 defined by considering the producer datasheet (PTT MCC Biochem, 2023). Briefly, PBS
172 was dried at 80°C for 5 hours in an oven. The materials were extruded in a twin-screw
173 extruder, model DR.16.AX (AX Plásticos Máquinas Técnicas Ltda, Diadema, Brasil), co-
174 rotating, screw diameter (D) of 16 mm and relation length/diameter (L/D) of 40, using a

175 temperature profile of 120/135/140/160/165/170/175/165°C and screw speed of 120 rpm.
 176 The literature (Wang et al., 2019; Possari et al., 2021) refers to the temperature of PBS
 177 processing around 150°C. The extruded filament was granulated using a granulator with
 178 rotating blades coupled to the extruder (AX Plásticos Máquinas Técnicas Ltda, Diadema,
 179 Brazil), and they were dried for 8 hours at 80°C to remove moisture.
 180 The formulations of bio-composites are shown in **Table 1**. The percentage of Cana fiber
 181 was 30 wt% for PBS only and for other formulations were 25 wt% of Cana with 5 wt%
 182 of Lig. These percentages were defined based on pre-tests, which found that more than
 183 30 wt% of Cana made extrusion difficult to control. MMT and SEP were added over the
 184 PBS/Cana/Lig mixture at 1.17% (codified as MMT1 or SEP1) and 1.72% w/w (codified
 185 as MMT2.5 or SEP2.5) with respect to PBS content in each mixture.
 186 **Table 1:** Formulation of bio-composites.

Sample ID	% (w/w)			
	PBS	Cana	Lig	Clay
Neat PBS (extruded)	100	0	0	0
PBS/Cana	70.0	30.0	0	0
PBS/Cana/Lig	70.0	25.0	5.0	0
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1	69.2	24.7	4.9	1.2
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5	68.8	24.6	4.9	1.7
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP1	69.2	24.7	4.9	1.2
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5	68.8	24.6	4.9	1.7

187 For the mechanical characterization, the granulated samples were molded in ISO format
 188 test specimen (ISO 527-1, 2012), using an injection molding machine, with temperature
 189 profile 150/160/170/180°C, holding pressure of 700 bar, for 12 seconds, injection
 190 pressure of 800 bar and flow rate of 40 cm³/s. For thermal tests, scanning electron
 191 microscopy (SEM) and melt flow tests, granulated samples were used.

192 2.3. Characterization

193 2.3.1. Mechanical Properties

194 The tensile test was carried out in a universal testing machine EMIC DL-2000 (Instron
195 Brasil Scientific Equipment Ltda, São Paulo, Brazil), with 9 kN load cell, according to
196 the ISO 527-1 (ISO 527-1, 2012) standard with atmosphere of $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $50 \pm 10\%$
197 relative humidity. Specimen size 1A, gauge length of 50 mm and speed of 5 mm/min.
198 Young's modulus, yield stress, yield elongation, tensile strength and elongation at break
199 was obtained to study tensile properties, using at least five specimens for each sample.

200 The flexural properties were also measured using a universal testing machine EMIC DL-
201 2000, with 9 kN load cell (Instron Brasil Scientific Equipment Ltda, São Paulo, Brazil),
202 speed 2 mm/min, maximum displacement of 20 mm, according to the ISO 178:2019
203 standards (ISO 178, 2019), length of span between supports 64 mm. The parameters
204 analyzed were flexural modulus, and flexural strength.

205 The Izod impact test was performed according to ISO 180 (ISO 180, 2019), at 23°C , in
206 an EMIC impact instrument, samples notched (2 mm deep) in a notch sample making
207 machine, model X1S-V (Philpolymer Engineering Thermoplastics Inc, São Roque,
208 Brazil). The hardness SHORE D were measured using Bareiss HPE II Shore D (Bareiss
209 Prüfgerätebau GmbH, Oberdischingen, Germany). The mechanical properties of the
210 composites were also compared to EP-440L polypropylene resin (PP) used to produce
211 tubes for seeding for agriculture.

212 *2.3.2. Melting Flow Rate*

213 The behavior of molten composites was evaluated by melting flow rate analysis (MFR)
214 using a plastometer (Maqtest Ltda, Franca, Brazil), according to ISO 1133 part I (ISO
215 1133-1, 2011), at 190°C and 2.16 kg.

216 *2.3.3. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)*

217 The FT-IR spectra of the samples were obtained to evaluate changes in the chemical
218 structure of the composite constituents. For this purpose, a Thermo Scientific FT-IR

219 spectrometer, model Nicolet iS10 (Massachusetts, EUA), in ATR mode, wavenumber
220 range 4000-400 cm^{-1} , diamond crystal, flat tip, ambient temperature and sample in powder
221 or pellet form was used.

222 2.3.4. Thermal Analysis

223 The melt and crystallization of PBS and composites was measured by differential
224 scanning calorimetry (DSC), model Q10 (TA Instruments, New Castle, USA), using
225 about 5 mg of sample in a sealed aluminum pan, under N_2 flow (50.0 mL/min). The
226 samples were first heated from 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and kept for 3 min to remove previous
227 thermal history, then cooled to 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and reheated to 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and cooled to 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, with a
228 heating/cooling rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The second scan was recorded for data analysis. The
229 degree of crystallinity (X_C) of PBS was calculated following equation Eq.1.

230

$$X_C (\%) = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_m^{\circ} \times W_{PBS}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

231

232 where X_C is the degree of crystallinity of PBS, ΔH_m° is the enthalpy of fusion of 100%
233 crystalline PBS (200 $\text{J}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) (Lule et al., 2020), ΔH_m is the melting enthalpy of the PBS
234 composites obtained by integral of melting peak of PBS on DSC curve, and W_{PBS} is the
235 weight fraction of PBS in the composites.

236 The thermal stability was evaluated by thermo-gravimetry analysis (TGA) in a model
237 Thermal Analysis System TGA/DSC 3+ (Mettler Toledo, Columbus, USA), the samples
238 were heated from room temperature (28 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) to 950 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, air flow
239 of 50 mL/min.

240 2.3.5. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

241 The structure of PBS and composite components were investigated by XRD analysis,
242 especially regarding to the change in the d -value of the crystalline planes of the clay

243 lamellae, which is indicative of dispersion of the clays due to the exfoliation in PBS. The
244 samples were grounded and sieved in mesh 100 to obtain a fine powder. The analysis was
245 carried out in XRD-6000 diffractometer (Shimadzu, Kyoto-Japan), scan range from 2° to
246 45° and 2.0°/min (scanning rate), source Cu tube and radiation wavelength (λ) of
247 0.154056 nm.

248 *2.3.6. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM–EDS)*

249 The fractured surface of the impact test specimens of the composite samples were
250 characterized through Jeol JSM-5800 LV scanning electron microscopy (SEM), equipped
251 with an Energy Dispersive X-ray Microanalysis system (EDS), (JEOL Ltd, Tokio, Japan),
252 with accelerating voltage of 3 to 20 kV, in order to analyze the morphology and adhesion
253 of the polymer matrix to the fibers. EDS detector was used to study elemental and
254 mapping composition of composite (clay, Lig, and natural fibers).

255 *2.3.7. Statistical Analysis*

256 The data were submitted to the Tukey test to verify significant differences between the
257 averages using Statistica 7.1 (StatSoft, Inc., Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA). Mean values
258 followed by the same letters in the same column do not differ at the 5% significance level
259 (Tukey, $p < 0.05$). The letters are in ascending order of mean values. This procedure aims
260 to ascertain the presence or absence of significant heterogeneity in the sample means.

261 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

262 *3.1. Melt Flow Rate (MFR)*

263 MFR values determined for each bio-composite are gathered in **Table 2**, that shows the
264 mean value and deviation bar for 10 replicated analyses. The incorporation of Cana fiber
265 led to a reduction in MFR compared to neat PBS, due to a restriction in the fiber's fluidity.
266 In other words, Cana fibers limited the MFR, and no reliable value was obtained.
267 However, the addition of Lig increased the MFR, though not sufficiently to reach the

268 original MFR value of neat PBS. In any case, these results demonstrate the lubricating
 269 effect of Lig in the melting state of PBS, reducing the viscosity value, thus counteracting
 270 the fluidity problems of PBS/Cana.

271 At first sight, the addition of clay minerals (MMT and SEP) had minimum influence in
 272 the melt viscosity (**Table 2**). Results seemed to indicate that smaller clay percentages
 273 (PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1 and PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP1) tend to increase the MFR values with
 274 respect to their counterparts using 1.72% of clay mineral. Despite this trend, the statistical
 275 analysis did not show significant differences between PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1 nor
 276 PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5 with respect to PBS/Cana/Lig ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$ and $F < F_{\text{critical}}$).
 277 On the contrary, the ANOVA test for PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP (both samples, with 1.17% and
 278 1.72% wt of sepiolite) compared to the PBS/Cana/Lig sample, revealed significant
 279 differences ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$ and $F > F_{\text{critical}}$) in the mean MFR values, indicating that SEP
 280 increased the MFR compared to the sample without clay.

281 High melt fluidity is important for processability, especially for the injection molding
 282 process (Possari et al., 2021). For comparison, the polypropylene EP440L resin has an
 283 MFR of 6.0 g/10min (230°C/2.16kg), despite the lower test temperature for PBS (190°C),
 284 which still presented higher MFR values than polypropylene EP440L.

285 **Table 2:** MFR results of PBS and composites.

Samples	MFR (g/10 min)
Neat PBS	35.5 ± 0.7^a
PBS/Cana	0.0^d
PBS/Cana/Lig	15.6 ± 0.9^c
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1	16.8 ± 1.0^c
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5	15.6 ± 1.3^c
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP1	24.5 ± 1.0^b
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5	16.9 ± 1.1^c

286 Note 1: Tukey statistical test, mean value with same superscript letters do not differ at the 5% significance
 287 level The letters are in ascending order of mean values. Number of replicates n=10. Note 2: PBS/Cana had
 288 an MFR result equal to zero.

289

290 3.2. Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

291 The FT-IR spectrum obtained allows analyzing the chemical structure of composite
292 components and their interactions. **Figure 1A** shows that Cana has a band around 3400–
293 3200 cm^{-1} attributed to hydrogen bonded –OH stretching vibration (Liu et al., 2009), or
294 due free water (moisture) presence (Zhang and Zhang, 2016). MMT are recognized at the
295 overlapping bands of 1042 cm^{-1} (Si-O), 880 cm^{-1} (Al-O-H), and 800 cm^{-1} (Al-Mg-O-H)
296 (Phua et al., 2011). Sepiolite has bands in 3616 cm^{-1} corresponding to the OH stretching
297 vibrations from $\text{Mg}_3\text{O-H}$, in 1656 cm^{-1} due vibrational distortion of water inside the
298 structure, 980, 1010 and 1206 cm^{-1} attributed to Si-O bonds within silica tetrahedra
299 (Chikh et al., 2016). PBS has bands around 1710 cm^{-1} related to the C=O stretching
300 vibration of ester group (Zhang and Zhang, 2016; Zhu et al., 2017), in 1330 cm^{-1} and 2945
301 cm^{-1} were assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric deformational vibrations of $-\text{CH}_2-$
302 groups and in 1144-1152 cm^{-1} due the $-\text{C-O-C}-$ stretching in the ester linkages (Phua et
303 al., 2011). As can see in **Figure 1A to 1D** the position of 1714 cm^{-1} band of neat PBS did
304 not change position in the composite but appeared a little shoulder at 1602-1608 cm^{-1}
305 with adding both clays, this corresponding to the hydrogen-bonded carbonyl groups
306 (Chikh et al., 2016), indicating the existence of interactions between clays and PBS.

307

(A)

(B)

308

309
 310
 311
 312 **Figure 1.** FT-IR spectrum of (A) PBS-MMT composites; (B) PBS-SEP composites. (C)
 313 and (D) shows that a shoulder appeared at 1602-1608 cm^{-1} in the composites.

314 3.3. Mechanical characterization

315 The tensile test curves (**Figure 2**) of the hybrid bio-composite shows an increase in
 316 Young's modulus and yield stress (**Table 3**) observed with the addition of Cana, as
 317 expected, as natural fibers in general have reinforcing capacity, which is why they are
 318 used in composites. Lig further contributes to the enhancement of the composite's yield
 319 strength. However, MMT seems to exert no significant effect on tensile stress and yield
 320 stress (ANOVA showing no significant difference in mean value). On the other hand, the
 321 hybrid composite with the presence of SEP slightly increases the tensile strength, yield
 322 stress and Young's modulus values with respect to PBS/Cana/Lig and PBS/Cana (**Table**
 323 **3**). This indicates a better interaction of SEP with PBS, perhaps being favored over MMT
 324 due to its greater surface area and its morphology composed of a fibrous structure with
 325 micropores and needle-like morphology with silanol groups (Si-OH) on its surface (Huo
 326 et al., 2017), resulting in a better interaction between inorganic fiber and organic polymer
 327 matrix and improvement in these properties. In all composites, the elongation at break
 328 decreased compared to neat PBS (**Table 3**). These results are probably due to the
 329 significant Cana fiber content (30 wt.%), which already promotes a high increase in the
 330 PBS/Cana modulus compared to pure PBS (+350%) and in the yield stress (+162%),

331 which may have masked or overlapped the effect of the clays. Someya et al. 2003, for
 332 example, obtained an increase from 700 MPa to 1000 MPa using 3 wt.% of modified
 333 MMT in PBS (Someya et al., 2003), and in the present study the increase obtained with
 334 the use of Cana was from 666 MPa to 2350 MPa. The EP440L resin exhibits a yield
 335 strength of 24 MPa and a yield elongation of 6%. According to the present results, the
 336 yield strength of pure PBS (11 MPa) is lower than that of EP440L. Nevertheless, the
 337 addition of Cana fiber, Lig, and ultimately SEP, elevates these values to a maximum of
 338 21.7 MPa, thus being closer to EP440L.

339

340 **Figure 2:** Tensile test curves for Neat PBS and composites.

341 **Table 3:** Tensile parameters results.

Samples	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Yield Stress (MPa)	Yield elongation (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
Neat PBS	666 ± 9.0 ^e	11.0 ± 0.5 ^d	1.85 ± 0.06 ^a	33.7 ± 0.6 ^a	16.83 ± 2.38 ^a
PBS/Cana	2350 ± 51.4 ^a	17.7 ± 0.6 ^c	0.95 ± 0.02 ^c	26.8 ± 0.3 ^d	2.53 ± 0.10 ^b
PBS/Cana/Lig	2119 ± 30.1 ^c	20.3 ± 0.5 ^{a,b}	1.16 ± 0.03 ^b	29.2 ± 0.3 ^{b,c}	2.53 ± 0.03 ^b
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1	2026 ± 25.7 ^d	20.0 ± 0.6 ^b	1.18 ± 0.05 ^b	28.9 ± 0.5 ^{c,d}	2.61 ± 0.19 ^b
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5	1966 ± 22.1 ^d	19.5 ± 0.6 ^{b,c}	1.19 ± 0.02 ^b	29.4 ± 0.2 ^{b,c}	2.93 ± 0.25 ^b
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP1	2210 ± 29.6 ^b	20.8 ± 0.6 ^{a,b}	1.15 ± 0.03 ^b	30.1 ± 0.4 ^{b,c}	2.65 ± 0.08 ^b
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5	2309 ± 28.6 ^a	21.7 ± 0.7 ^a	1.14 ± 0.08 ^b	31.3 ± 1.0 ^b	2.59 ± 0.14 ^b

342 Note: Tukey statistical test, mean value with same superscript letters in the same column do not differ at
 343 the 5% significance level. The letters are in ascending order of mean values. Mean values ± s.d. (n = 5).

344 Neat PBS yield elongation was 1.85%, although the inclusion of Cana resulted in a

345 decrease to 0.95. Generally, the addition of natural fiber negatively affects the mechanical

346 properties of composite, reducing ductility and in some cases the strength, because

347 composites are strongly dependent on fiber content, compatibility, interfacial adhesion,
348 that can cause formation of aggregates, voids in the composite structure, and little bonding
349 between filler and polymer (Platnieks et al., 2020), this is in agreement with the results
350 obtained here with the incorporating of up to 30 wt.% fiber, which leads to a reduction
351 of elongation capacity in the composites compared to the neat PBS. The incorporation of
352 Lig partially offsets the reduction in deformation, whereas clays appear to have negligible
353 impact (**Table 3**). In terms of yield elongation, neat PBS exhibit lower values than
354 EP440L (its yield elongation being 6%). Contrary to the yield tension, the introduction of
355 Cana and Lig do not approach elongation values closer to EP440L.

356 The impact resistance of the composite decreases with the addition of Cana when
357 compared to neat PBS, and the inclusion of Lig further reduces impact resistance. Some
358 authors only show the tensile properties results and do not show impact resistance results
359 for PBS-MMT composites (Ojijo and Ray, 2014; Tian et al., 2016), and other shows that
360 impact strength was reduced with addition of 2 wt.% of MMT (unmodified) in PBS (Phua
361 et al., 2011), which the impact strength reduced from 8.78 kJ/m² to 8.3 kJ/m². In particular
362 case, the decrease in impact strength of the composites could be attributed to the
363 significant Cana fiber content (>30 wt.%), which could have led to difficulties in
364 incorporation into PBS and poor fiber-polymer interfacial adhesion. The addition of clay
365 minerals (MMT or SEP) did not influence this parameter, as illustrated in (**Table 4**). The
366 large amount of Cana fiber may be overriding the impact resistance results with the use
367 of other additives (Lig and clays), without any improvements being observed. In fact, the
368 ANOVA test indicates no significant difference in impact resistance between the
369 PBS/Cana/Lig samples with and without the clays. These findings suggest that Lig does
370 not function as a plasticizer—which would typically increase both melt flow rate (MFR)
371 and impact resistance—but as a lubricant. The EP440L resin remained intact under impact

372 at 23°C, showing no signs of rupture. In general composites with natural fiber show brittle
 373 tensile behavior, caused by the formation of aggregates, voids in the composite's
 374 structure, and weak bonding between filler and polymer, furthermore, pure thermoplastic
 375 represents a continuous material, while composites present two phases, inherently
 376 presenting some discontinuities, which can lead to the initiation of crack propagation
 377 (Frollini et al., 2013).

378 **Table 4:** Impact resistance and hardness Shore D results.

Samples	Impact Resistance (KJ/m ²)	Hardness Shore D
Neat PBS	19.4 ± 0.3 ^a	67.6 ± 0.3 ^c
PBS/Cana	16.5 ± 0.5 ^b	70.7 ± 1.2 ^{a, b}
PBS/Cana/Lig	15.6 ± 0.3 ^{b, c}	69.6 ± 0.6 ^{a, b, c}
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1	15.2 ± 0.2 ^{b, c}	70.6 ± 1.2 ^b
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5	15.1 ± 0.2 ^{b, c}	70.5 ± 1.2 ^{a, b}
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP1	14.6 ± 0.2 ^c	68.9 ± 0.7 ^{a, c}
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5	14.7 ± 0.3 ^c	70.3 ± 1.4 ^{a, b}

379 Note: Tukey statistical test, mean value with same superscript letters in the same column do not differ at
 380 the 5% significance level. The letters are in ascending order of mean values. Mean values ± s.d. (n = 5).
 381

382 The hardness of PBS composites increased by use of the main additives (Cana and Lig).
 383 According to results, it is possible to hypothesize that the ingredient responsible for
 384 hardness increase is Cana, the highest value reported for PBS/Cana. Moreover, Cana is
 385 present in all composites, explaining why the hardness Shore D values remained higher
 386 than neat PBS. Lig and clays have little or no effect on hardness (**Table 4**).

387 Flexural tests are important for the application, its results gathered in **Figure 3** and **Table**
 388 **5**, which shows the average curves of each sample. The flexural modulus is a critical
 389 parameter for material application. As demonstrated by the data, the flexural modulus and
 390 flexural strength (**Table 5**) increase across all composite formulations when compared to
 391 neat PBS. The inclusion of Lig is observed to decrease the flexural modulus relative to
 392 composites containing Cana. Clays exert a minor influence, slightly enhancing the
 393 flexural modulus and strength. The flexural modulus of pure PBS is recorded at 664 MPa,

394 which is lower than the 1050 MPa of the EP440L resin, indicating insufficient flexural
 395 stiffness. However, the bio-composites exhibit flexural modulus values ranging from
 396 2275 MPa (PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1) to 2462 MPa (PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5), surpassing the
 397 EP440L. This suggests the potential for reducing the flexural modulus through additives
 398 such as plasticizers, which could improve impact resistance and yield elongation values,
 399 currently lower than those of EP440L.

400

401

402 **Figure 3.** Flexural test curves (each curve is an average of 5 samples tested).

403 **Table 5:** Flexural parameters resulted of tests.

Samples	Flexural Modulus (MPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)
Neat PBS	35.2 ± 1.4 ^d	664 ± 38 ^d
PBS/Cana	52.7 ± 0.6 ^a	2588 ± 19 ^c
PBS/Cana/Lig	54.2 ± 1.0 ^c	2333 ± 53 ^{b, c}
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1	53.4 ± 1.1 ^c	2275 ± 36 ^c
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5	54.6 ± 0.2 ^c	2322 ± 59 ^{a, b, c}
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP1	55.7 ± 1.1 ^c	2334 ± 45 ^{a, b}
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5	56.6 ± 0.5 ^b	2462 ± 26 ^a

404 Note: Tukey statistical test, mean value with same superscript letters in the same column do not differ at
 405 the 5% significance level. The letters are in ascending order of mean values. Mean values ± s.d. (n = 5).
 406

407 **3.4. Thermal analysis**

408 The thermal stability of polymer materials influences their flame retardancy and thermal
 409 degradation characteristics. Consequently, analyzing thermal stability is an effective

410 method for evaluating these properties. According to literature (Frollini et al., 2013;
411 Liminana et al., 2018), degradation of a lignocellulosic filler takes place in four different
412 stages: water removal (50-60 °C), hemicellulose degradation (300-320 °C), cellulose
413 degradation (345-365 °C) and, finally, Lig degradation ($T > 400$ °C). The weight loss
414 around 180.0 °C is ascribed to dehydration of chemically bonded water and hydroxyl
415 groups in Lig, resulting in a mass loss of about 5%. A minor shoulder at about 285.5 °C
416 (**Figure 4B**) is attributed to the partial decomposition of carboxylic and anhydride groups
417 and the decomposition of the residual hemicellulose in Kraft Lig, with mass loss about
418 6.7%. The maximum Lig mass loss occurs between 290 °C and 600 °C which corresponds
419 to the pyrolysis of Lig (Yan et al., 2021). Lig degradation generates water, methanol, CO,
420 and CO₂ (Liminana et al., 2018). According to the literature, the degradation of PBS
421 occurs as chain degradation, exhibits a single stage degradation (single DTG peak) and
422 starts at approximately 280-300°C, with a peak at 410°C, and the decomposition is almost
423 complete at 430-440°C (mass loss >90 wt%) (Frollini et al., 2013). The TGA
424 thermograms in **Figure 4A** shows that mass loss starts in around 240 °C and the values
425 of temperature of mass loss of 5 wt% ($T_{WL5\%}$), 50wt% ($T_{WL50\%}$), 90%wt ($T_{WL90\%}$),
426 maximum mass loss (T_{max}), temperature at peak of mass loss rate (T_d) of PBS and
427 composites are presented in **Table 6**. The temperature at peak (T_d) of mass degradation
428 can be found in DTG analysis (**Figure 4B**).

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(A)

(B)

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436 **Figure 4.** (A) Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), and (B) Differential
437 Thermogravimetric (DTG) Analysis.

438 **Table 6:** Degradation results parameters of TGA analysis.

Sample	$T_{WL5\%}$ (°C)	$T_{WL50\%}$ (°C)	$T_{WL90\%}$ (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_d (peak) (°C)	Residual Mass (%)
Neat PBS	329.7	394.2	418.2	424.3	402.6	0.14
PBS/Cana	292.0	387.5	447.8	470.9	392.8	1.06
PBS/Cana/Lig	315.6	393.2	479.9	507.8	395.5	0.63
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1	297.2	389.3	463.0	489.6	391.6	1.51
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5	291.8	386.7	459.4	483.7	390.5	2.36
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP1	291.5	386.9	466.4	492.2	393.2	1.77
PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5	284.4	385.1	468.7	493.3	389.1	3.77

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440 As can be seen in **Table 6**, $T_{WL5\%}$ and $T_{WL50\%}$ of PBS/Cana and PBS/Cana/Lig were
441 smaller than neat PBS, somewhat expected since Cana and Lig are organic compounds

442 that usually degrade at lower temperatures than neat PBS. Moreover, the addition of clay
443 particles to these composites further reduces $T_{WL5\%}$ and $T_{WL50\%}$ with respect to neat PBS.
444 MMT and SEP are inorganic minerals whose thermal events are mainly due to water loss
445 (free water, bound water) from 30-500°C and dehydroxylation from 500°C (SEP) and
446 600°C (MMT) (García-Quiles et al., 2019; García-Villén et al., 2019, 2020)(García-
447 Quiles et al., 2019; García-Villén et al., 2019). In all cases, the weight loss experienced
448 by clays during these events is minimum (2-7%, depending on the environmental
449 conditions in which they were preserved until use). The evaporation of water bound to
450 clay structures can be explaining by the decrease in $T_{WL5\%}$ and $T_{WL50\%}$. A decrease in
451 degradation temperature of the organic compounds (Cana and Lig) can also be feasible,
452 since the presence of clay particles can “disperse” organic molecules in the composite
453 structure, making them more susceptible to thermal degradation.

454 The $T_{WL90\%}$ increased with Cana, Lig and clays addition, from 418.2°C for neat PBS to
455 around 460~470°C for the rest of the composites. The T_{max} has a more significant increase
456 in composites (around 490°C) compared with neat PBS (424.3°C). More into detail, SEP
457 is slightly better in terms of thermal stability compared with MMT because the T_{max} of
458 SEP composites are around 492~493°C, while MMT ones are around 483~489°C. By the
459 same token $T_{WL90\%}$ values of SEP are higher than MMT composites (466~468°C for SEP
460 and 459~463°C for MMT). The residual mass result obtained by TGA analysis seems
461 consistent with the content of the materials. Neat PBS presented a very low residual
462 (0.14%). The addition of Cana fiber (30 wt.%) resulted in a residual of 1.06%, indicating
463 a low ash content. The residual of the PBS/Cana/Lig sample had a slight decrease
464 (0.63%), perhaps it is due to the smaller amount of Cana that was replaced by the Lig
465 mass. An increase in the residual is observed in the other samples due to the addition of
466 clays. The DSC curves (**Figure 5A**) show two main peaks, one endothermic peak at

467 115.0°C (for neat PBS) that can be attributed to a crystalline melting transformation (T_m)
468 and other peak (exothermic) at 72.7°C (for neat PBS), corresponding to crystallization of
469 PBS. The T_m values of PBS (around 115°C) did not change with the addition of Cana, Lig
470 and clays (**Figure 5B** and **Table 7**), but SEP caused the appearance of a small peak at
471 103-104°C, while for neat PBS and other composites appear a shoulder (near 110°C).
472 Several authors (Liang et al., 2009; Liminana et al., 2018; Arabeche et al., 2022) reported
473 that PBS can present three peaks (T_{m1} , T_{m2} and T_{m3}), the main and higher temperature T_m
474 peak (T_{m1}) is not related to the crystallization of previous cooling process and attributed
475 to the recrystallization of the partially melted crystals during heating process (melting–
476 recrystallization–remelting process). The other small T_m peaks (T_{m2} and T_{m3}) are possibly
477 attributed to the melting of original crystals with different crystalline lamella distribution
478 with different thermal stabilities. The appearance of the T_{m3} peak when SEP is added to
479 PBS is a strong indication of good SEP-PBS interaction, since T_{m3} peak is attributed to the
480 formation of original crystals in the interfacial region between the clay and the polymer
481 (Arabeche et al., 2022), while the melting temperature T_{m1} remains unchanged. This can
482 denote a good dispersion of SEP and its ability to crystallize at its interface. PBS has a
483 low crystallization temperature (72.7°C) (**Figure 5C** and **Table 7**) but the peak shifted to
484 a higher temperature with the addition of Cana, Lig and MMT (around 78°C), and
485 increased further with the addition of SEP (around 86 °C), indicating that the
486 crystallization rate of PBS was enhanced with the addition of these, especially SEP. The
487 increase in PBS crystallization can be attributed to the effect of fillers such as natural fiber
488 and clays on the nucleation of crystallization (Liang et al., 2009).

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(B)

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(C)

504 **Figure 5.** Comprehensive DSC Analysis of PBS Composites: (A) Full Thermal Profiles;
 505 (B) Detailed View of the Melting Temperature Region; (C) Detailed View of
 506 Crystallization Region.

507 **Table 7:** parameters result of DSC analysis.

Sample	T_c (°C)	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)	X_c (%)
Neat PBS	72.7	115.0	67.17	33.6%
PBS/Cana	77.3	115.2	54.48	38.9%
PBS/Cana/Lig	77.7	114.7	55.30	39.5%
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT1	76.8	115.1	52.08	37.6%
PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5	77.7	114.3	54.57	39.5%
PBS/Cana/Lig/Sep1	86.0	114.6	56.55	40.9%
PBS/Cana/Lig/Sep2.5	86.4	115.0	53.05	38.4%

508 The melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) and degree of crystallinity (X_c) increased with the addition
 509 of Cana, Lig, and clays (**Table 5**), possibly enhanced by the nucleation effect of these
 510 components. Some studies found that the degree of crystallinity of PBS increases with
 511 the content of cellulose filler, achieving 35% of crystallinity with 30% of natural fiber
 512 (Liang et al., 2009).

513 3.5. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

514 The XRD diagrams of clays, neat PBS and composites are shown in **Figure 6A** (with
 515 MMT) and **6B** (with SEP). Native sepiolite has characteristics reflections are in the planes
 516 (1 1 0), (0 4 0) and (4 0 0) at $2\theta = 7.2^\circ$, 19.6° , 26.5° , respectively (Nikolic et al., 2017).
 517 MMT exhibits a broad reflection at $2\theta = 6.08^\circ$, corresponding to the 0 0 1 basal reflection
 518 with a d_{001} -value of 1.45 nm (Phua et al., 2011).

519 Analyzing XRD diagrams, MMT presents a reflection for (0 0 1) plan at $2\theta = 5.3^\circ$
 520 corresponding to a d-value of 1.67 nm, calculated using Bragg condition, $n\lambda=2.d.\sin(\theta)$,
 521 but the composite did not present that plane (0 0 1) (**Figure 6A**), Some authors (Someya
 522 et al., 2003; Chen et al., 2015; Soares et al., 2017) show that the absence of this reflection
 523 in the composite, strongly indicates a exfoliation of the clay, especially below 5 wt.% of
 524 MMT. This is an indicative of achievement of MMT exfoliation in

525 PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5 composites, but it was not confirmed by improvements in other
526 properties (mechanical for example), perhaps due to the large dosage of Cana fiber, which
527 ended up overlapping its effect.

528 Related to SEP, the reflection 2θ for (1 1 0) plan in the composite, changed a little (7.3°
529 to 7.1°), this represents a d_{001} -value varying from 1.210 nm to 1.244 nm ($\Delta d = 0.034$ nm),
530 and the approximate width of the extended molecular chain of PBS is about 0.4 – 0.6 nm
531 (Someya et al., 2003), then Δd is lower than the width of the PBS, indicating that PBS
532 did not intercalated into SEP interlayer space.

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536 **Figure 6.** XRD diagrams of (A) MMT, PBS and composite; (B) SEP, PBS and composite.

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538 3.6. Morphology Analysis

539 The morphology of the samples after break (at Izod impact test) were studied by SEM.

540 PBS/Cana composites (**Figure 7A**) show the presence of Cana fibers embedded in the

541 PBS matrix. It is possible to observe in some images (**Figures 7A, C and D**) that the Cana

542 fibers detach from the polymer matrix, indicating a certain lack of fiber-matrix adhesion,

543 resulting in low impact resistance. As explained previously, this may be due to the high

544 percentage of Cana fiber used (up to 30 wt.%), which may have led to its poor

545 incorporation into the PBS. In addition, the low natural fiber-polymer interaction is

546 already widely reported in the literature due to the hydrophilic character of cellulose in
547 natural fibers that contain hydroxyl groups and the hydrophobic character of polymers
548 (Miao and Hamad, 2013), causing a certain incompatibility that can be minimized by
549 using various methods to improve this interaction, such as the use of compatibilizing
550 agents, functionalization, chemical treatment of the fibers, etc (Platnieks et al., 2020).
551 PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5 composite images are gathered in **Figure 7C**, whereas **Figure**
552 **7D** correspond to PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5. As happened for the rest of the samples, Cana
553 fibers are visible after the impact test. Although clay mineral particles are not
554 distinguishable by this SEM analysis, EDS analysis (**Figure 7E** and **F**) proved their
555 presence by the detection of Si and Mg, and sulfur is supposed to be from Lig. The
556 distribution of these elements (Si, Mg, Al, S) in the composite can be seen by EDS map
557 image of PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5 sample, is available in **SM2**, which presents a good
558 dispersion of the clay in the PBS matrix due to the good shear mixing promoted by the
559 twin screw extruder processing. Nevertheless, by taking a closer look to the PBS textural
560 aspect, a more compact PBS matrix can be detected in samples with clays when compared
561 to PBS/Cana and PBS/Cana/Lig. These morphologies are somewhat coherent with impact
562 test results, indicating that the addition of MMT and SEP reduced the impact resistance
563 of the composites, even if no statistically significant differences were found.

564

565

566 **Figure 7.** SEM images and EDS and microanalysis of composites. (A) PBS/Cana. (B)

567 PBS/Cana/Lig. (C) PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5. (D) PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5. (E) EDS

568 microanalysis for PBS/Cana/Lig/MMT2.5. (F) EDS microanalysis for

569 PBS/Cana/Lig/SEP2.5.

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571 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

572 In the present study, naturally occurring residues and natural clay minerals are combined
573 and proposed as functional ingredients of biodegradable composites for agricultural use.
574 Polybutylene succinate (PBS) was chosen as the main polymer due to its biodegradability,
575 although its properties require further enhancement with the use of other environmentally
576 friendly ingredients, such as canabrava (Cana), lignin (Lig), montmorillonite (MMT) and
577 sepiolite (SEP). Polypropylene resin EP440L was used as a reference standard due to its
578 common application in seedling production. The addition of 30% Cana reduced the melt
579 flow rate (MFR) of the PBS composite; however, this effect was partially mitigated by
580 the lubricating effect of Lig and SEP, resulting in an MFR similar to that of EP440L.
581 Cana and SEP significantly increased the stiffness and flexural strength of the composites.
582 Thermal analyses revealed an increase in crystallization and thermal stability, with
583 sepiolite outperforming montmorillonite. Although the impact resistance of the
584 composites decreased, the results indicate that the incorporation of PBS with Cana, Lig,
585 and natural clays enhances the composite properties, thereby improving their efficacy and
586 environmental sustainability for agricultural use, particularly in seedling cultivation
587 processes.

588

589 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

590 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
591 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

592

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609

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